

Marteloscope

Introduction

A marteloscope is a practical tool for training in silvicultural management. In groups, participants walk through a forest plot and simulate thinning by choosing the trees that they think should be cut (hammering). Software then makes it possible to simulate the impact that this cutting would have on the forest: economic profitability, improvement in the quality of the wood in the long term, preservation of biodiversity, etc.

Methodology and results

The size of a Marteloscope should be fixed to 1 hectare with side lengths of 100 x 100 m. Size and form should be tailored to the planned use of the Marteloscope and the geography and local conditions. So, they may in exceptional cases differ from the regular rectangular shape.

A 1 ha plot (chestnut, oak and beech stand) for the marteloscope has been located in Corrèze at Meilhards. This site is now operational to welcome groups and to carry out hammering exercises (first day in April 2023).

In addition, 10 reference sites have been located in Dordogne. The interest of these reference sites is that they present a great diversity of types of chestnut stands (pure and mixed) of all ages as well as different types of management applied (renewal with stump crushing for example).

The interest of marteloscopes and reference sites is that they represent a practical tool for training in silvicultural management.

Figure 1. Example of the marteloscope tool, a training programme designed to analyse hammering. Sylvain Gaudin © CNPF

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

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<https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/sylviculture-de-pr%C3%A9cision-en-nouvelle->

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